

A photograph of a paper mill interior, showing complex machinery with pipes, railings, and structural beams. The scene is dimly lit with a purple tint. A white vertical machine component has the brand name "Fike" visible on it.

EXTRACTION OF WOOD FIBRES AND FINES FROM POST-CONSUMER FIBREBOARD

Post-consumer wood waste often contains fibreboard, a wood-based panel made of resin bound wood fibres. For the wood-based panel industry, this represents a potential feedstock, yet it is typically not recovered as a raw material, because it is less suitable for particleboard production, another panel type and the main material recycling route for recovered wood. As a result, fibreboard is often sorted out and sent to energy recovery, reducing the share of wood waste kept in material loops.

As virgin wood prices rise and raw materials become scarcer, interest is growing in using wood waste for higher value applications than just for particle board production, including new fibreboard. EcoReFibre has addressed this with an enhanced sorting line that separates fibreboard from mixed wood waste feeding into three processing routes. The following sections presents the wet and dry processes which recover the high-quality fibres for new fibreboard production, supporting a more circular wood-based panel value chain.

After sorting, fibreboard chips can be processed using two technologies: the so-called wet process and the dry process. EcoReFibre has demonstrated both processes using post-consumer fibreboard to produce high-quality secondary raw materials for wood-based panels. Both technologies reached Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6.

APPLICATION

The wet process is a batch process and can be integrated into existing fibreboard production lines. The dry process is a continuous process that can be integrated into particleboard plants.

WET PROCESS

In the wet process, saturated steam softens the chips under pressure, breaking down water soluble binders. A rapid pressure drop then releases the fibres and dries them, reducing moisture to below 15%. The fibres are then cleaned in a sifter to remove impurities such as metals, plastics and all kind of surface coatings. These fibres are ready to be used in the production of new fibreboards. The wet process can handle production residues from medium- and high- density fibreboards (MDF, HDF), laminate flooring and insulation boards.

ACHIEVEMENTS

The wet process treated more than 25 tonnes of post-consumer fibreboard chips and produced clean fibres suitable for new fibreboard, with quality compared to virgin fibres. The process tolerates contaminants (e.g. screws, plastic, coatings) to be removed afterward to meet required quality standards. It also showed economic advantages through lower thermal and electrical energy demand than fibreboard production from virgin wood. The technology is scalable, with industrial units available at 1.5 tonnes per hour and 4 tonnes per hour.

NEXT STEPS

In the wet process, future work includes testing a wider range of input materials, aiming the process to reliably handle pre- and post-consumer fibreboard (MDF, HDF), laminate flooring and insulation products. In parallel, further optimisation should focus on operating settings and plant layout to maximise fibre quality, impurity removal and integration into existing industrial lines.

DRY PROCESS

In the dry process, fibreboard chips are milled in a continuous process into fine particles with a defined particle size using a horizontally rotating tool. Because post-consumer fibreboard often has surface coatings, the chamber is designed to remove them during processing. Air currents lift coatings away from the milling zone, and an internal flap opens periodically to extract them pneumatically. The remaining material is then screened into three fractions: oversize, fines and dust. Oversize is recirculated for further milling. The fines and dust are collected as separate output streams.

ACHIEVEMENTS

The dry process processed more than 22 tonnes of post-consumer fibreboard chips. It produces fines with the required particle size distribution for particleboard surface layer, while separating coatings into a dedicated stream. The remaining dust can be used for Bioblocks, modular construction units developed in the EcoReFibre project.

NEXT STEPS

For the dry process, next steps include refining key settings, including rotation speed and screen mesh size to maximise output quality and quantity for downstream production.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based, carbon storing material wood is a key driver for Europe's circular bioeconomy. Reintegrating post-consumer fibreboards and other wood waste into production of new products helps closing material loops and extend the lifespan of wood. Through such horizontal recycling, the material value is maintained and the dependence on virgin wood is reduced.

An innovative waste sorting line and smart recycling technologies enable end-of-life wood-based panels to be broken down into fibres and particles which are then reintegrated into new panel production. Industrial trials have shown that MDF can incorporate up to 25% recycled wood while achieving performance similar to reference panels. From an economic perspective, increasing recycling can help broaden the raw material base and support stabilising volatile virgin wood prices. Of course, also investments in recycling equipment and process adaption are required for industrial-scale production.

By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP).

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

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